

E-Learning for Nurse Education: A Literature Review of Contemporary Issues and Challenges

The influence of E-Learning to enhance educational outcomes runs the gamut of economic sectors and is palpably manifest in nurse education and related healthcare training programs, offering an effective intervention to align prospective nurses with various rewarding careers. The insatiable demand for proficient nurses around the world has invoked a need for innovative E-Learning programs that effectively mobilize human resource from various backgrounds and regional origins, creating a global, yet communal platform for

comprehensive, innovative, and transferable nursing education. By such means, the human resource gap for competent nurses, precisely in remote, rural areas and developing countries, is addressed and deescalated. Contemporary research in E-Learning for nurse education concerns itself with the following primary research question (Farrell, 2006; Clark & Piercey, 2012; Wahl & Latayan, 2011):

How can E-Learning assist the field of nurse education to surmount its most critical, pressing challenges and issues?

The daunting complexity of this research required subdivisions of the E-Learning literature on nurse and healthcare education into a two-fold questions design that elucidated the most significant issues. Primarily, the contemporary nursing industry requires not only exceptionally well-trained nurses, but also an abundance of new nurses, stressing the demand to massively mobilize and

motivate potential nursing students. Therefore, the initial question explored issues revolving around morale-building, mentality-development, motivation, recruitment, and retention of diverse, globally scattered human resources for nursing careers. One of the questions, therefore, proceeded as follows: *How can E-Learning mobilize, motivate, and retain nursing students?*

Secondly, those potential students who finally do choose to become nurses will require comprehensive education and training to meet the demands of an industry that is persistently and rapidly evolving, upgrading, and changing to meet social and technological innovations. The extant E-Learning literature on the actual educational process of nursing and related healthcare practice continues to concern itself with programs and strategies to maintain motivation and retention, yet also seeks to transmit specialized knowledge

and skills, the upgrading of inadequate standards and procedures, as well as insights into the optimization for the

quality of nursing care.

The second research question, thus, proceeded as follows:

How can E-Learning effectively train, upgrade, and transmit specialized skills/knowledge?

These two central, synergistic questions emphasize the importance and significance of a robust, cutting-edge, and facilitative educational technology to maintain and optimize benchmarks in recruitment, retention, knowledge specialization, and continual training. The educational practice and resource of yesterday continues to exhibit acceptable results, yet the demand of today and the challenges of tomorrow have precipitated humanistic

“...technology to maintain and optimize benchmarks in recruitment, retention, knowledge specialization, and continual training...”

and digital technologies to complement what is good and time-proven about traditional education and to remain abreast

of the ever-growing, pressing demand for nurses and related healthcare professionals.

Consequently, the first segment of this literature review explored articles more specifically concerning themselves with matters pertaining to mobilization, motivation, and recruitment of potential nurses; the second segment interrogated the status on the knowledge acquisition of specialized skills and performances, as well as the periodic, significant demand to

upgrade such assets and to respond to change and innovation.

These pivotal questions reflect upon the effort of hypothesizing for E-Learning. Research topics can become more specialized and technical based on a demonstrably beneficial potential for quality upgrades (see Figure 1).

Mobilization, Motivation, and Retention of Nursing Students

Farrell (2006) surveyed current developments and trends related to E-Learning for nurse education, observing an inherently beneficial synergy. The pressing demand for trained, proficient nurses encourages dynamic, innovative learning environments.

While advances in technology promise

increasingly more interactivity and digital engagement, Farrell (2006) emphasized the

H1: E-Learning assists the field of nurse education to surmount its most critical, pressing challenges and issues.
H0: E-Learning does not assist the field of nurse education to surmount its most critical, pressing challenges and issues.

Figure 1: Research Hypotheses for Quality Upgrades

need to instill in students a conducive mentality that will optimally exploit E-Learning for personal and professional growth.

Any deficit in this preliminary motivational, morale-building, and empowerment phase will translate into

the oft-cited detriments and disadvantages to E-Learning: high drop-out rates, inability to maintain safe practice, and a resignation toward further E-Learning.

Furthermore, E-Learning researchers concern themselves extensively with the reasons for nurses' educational frustration and failure with the programs. Outcome questionnaires and surveys reveal that a lack of computer/IT literacy and access to electronic learning resources poses the most daunting challenge to effectiveness. Another attrition variable represents a sense of

disengagement with peers and society.

Some nurses report their E-Learning programs were more demanding than traditional lecture-based courses,

incorporating online discussion, feedback to peers, and submission of topic reviews.

E-Learning continues to suffer from a lack of credibility and from a skeptical resistance from clinical assessors and employers (Farrell, 2006).

As a result of the ever-increasing demand for nurses and the intimidating nature of E-Learning, pre-service nurses require E-Learning managers or mentors who will acclimatize students with the technology, offer support for motivation and morale-building, and certainly transmit the basic IT skills that will help build confidence and prompt pre-service nurses to take ownership of their learning.

The nurses who have met those fundamentals report enhanced, more customizable personal development (40% of participants), realization of specific interests (28% of participants), and relevance to their career aspirations (25% of participants) (Farrell, 2006).

Clark & Piercey (2012) confirm that proficiency with ICT and multimedia web-conferencing software will enhance motivation and retention of pre-service nurses in remote, rural areas, where a steadily growing population, but a lack of accredited brick-and-mortar healthcare schools, create fertile grounds for E-Learning opportunities. Web-conferencing mitigates and to some extent overcomes this impediment through its ability to simulate real-world situations and to connect participants regardless of spatial limitations.

Similarly, Frehywot, Vovides, Talib, Mikhail, Ross, Wohltjen & Scott (2013) conducted research on the status of E-Learning from a

developmental and structural perspective, addressing the critical personnel gap and the role E-Learning can fulfill in mitigating the shortage in low and middle-income countries (LMICs). They compiled an extensive literature review of the various E-Learning modalities used in such countries, observing that innovation and resourcefulness play a crucial role in motivating, recruiting, and retaining healthcare personnel. Partnerships between universities and hospitals and between low-income and wealthy countries introduce more effective, innovative E-Learning platforms, such as mobile learning and Tuft University's enterprise knowledge and curriculum management system, enabling a vast outreach of regionally and temporally limited lectures and presentations for LMIC's enhancement.

“The enhancement of healthcare professionals in LMICs... will entail a complex, interconnected support system...”

The enhancement of healthcare professionals in LMICs, according to the study, will entail a complex, interconnected support system, consisting of institutional support, faculty and student engagement, and ICT technical expertise infrastructure. The authors observed that, through an optimal coordination and mobilization of these constituents, LMICs will be able to allocate limited, transient funds to the most pressing, urgent issues, while still offering effective, high-quality training to get people working as quickly and efficiently as possible.

Although this described study contextualized nursing students within a complex support system, the students themselves often hold an additional key to effective motivation through peer-oriented and peer-developed

learning tools, which was explored in Windle, Lavery, Herman, Hallawell & Wharrad (2010).

Nursing students' insights and field experience working with patients and clients in various settings collaborate with tutors, instructional designers, and media specialists to give rise to so-called Reusable Learning Objects (RLOs), which represent narrative simulations of real-world, consequential issues that require nurses to develop dedicated coping skills and a responsibility ethic.

The study limited itself to RLOs in the context of nursing care for clients with moderate to severe learning disabilities, offering simulated journeys through the homes where such clients reside and offering diverse opportunities to optimize care centricism through an attention to clients' rights, communication, and heightened respect for their needs and wants. Multimedia RLOs are cost-effective and rewarding;

they enable current students to become creatively and actively involved with their own education and pass that experience on to their peers and research groups.

E-Learning Effectively Trains, Upgrades, and Transmits Specialized Skills/Knowledge

Wahl & Latayan (2011) evaluated an E-Learning initiative for nursing education that significantly increased access, flexibility, and self-determination for in-service nurses. The study represents an appraisal of a change management E-Learning project, shifting an annual quality assurance program from a traditional learning environment to an E-Learning platform.

Project administrators collected definitive outcome data that attested to improved performance and fiscal benchmarks. The non-random control group within the study represented the traditional

environment that had been administering the quality assurance program, based on a power-point presentation in a physical classroom during a fixed day and time. The

experimental group completed the same quality assurance training program, entitled the “Nursing Education Annual Requirements (NEAR),” through an online E-Learning format, granting temporal/spatial flexibility and incremental progress tracking.

The experimental group under the change-managed E-learning program yielded impressive and demonstrable qualitative

and quantitative data (see Figure 2).

Brown, Kirkpatrick, Mangum & Avery (2008) and Walsh (2011) explored the underlying theories and

impulses of narrative multimedia E-Learning tools, emphasizing the need to involve aspiring nursing students with the Humanities, fine arts, writing journalism, and motion pictures, also commonly referred to as narrative pedagogy. Traditional nursing education, limited to lectures and rote learning, has become inadequate to train and upgrade diverse students within a global information society.

As a result, increasingly more nurse educators incorporate students' innate

interest in relationships, stories, and digital media to enhance humanistic and philosophical awareness.

“Partnerships evolve naturally through narrative pedagogy among fellow students, faculty, clinicians, and patients in the spirit of a communal human condition, counteracting hierarchy, and routine interaction.”

Narrative pedagogy motivates contemporary nursing students to adopt an egalitarian, personable, and communicative mindset, exploring common perceptions and emotions to

improve nurse-patient relations.

Partnerships evolve naturally through narrative pedagogy among fellow students, faculty, clinicians, and patients in the spirit of a communal human condition, counteracting hierarchy, and routine interaction. The research contends that an immersion in art, film, literature, storytelling, and reflective journal writing will motivate students to become responsible, dedicated healthcare professionals, and the peer-oriented study took this trend to an additional level of interactive digital edutainment. Since the field of nursing and care provisioning has become inscrutably complex and diffuse, emphasis has shifted on self-government and professional ownership among students.

Finally, the most interactive, motivational,

and self-deterministic form of E-Learning for nurse education represent digital games, which incorporate the narrative pedagogy framework and real-world, peer-oriented simulation features. In fact, digital game-based learning research has identified unique, salient benefits to sophisticated games that immerse students in an interactive, goal-oriented, and manipulative 3D digital environment, where they can hone their skills with simulated patients and standard procedures.

The research indicated freshmen nursing students will build their confidence and

identities through the experiential, consequential, yet non-punitive learning paradigm. In other words, the intimidating complexity of the nursing world is put at students' fingertips to liberally explore and manipulate, and a variety of contemporary, universal soft-skills, as reflection, critical thinking, conflict resolution, and multicultural understanding are similarly facilitated and effectively transmitted, contributing to career transferability and professional preparedness (Lynch-Sauer, VandenBosch, Kron, Gjerde, Arato, Sen & Fetters, 2011).

- An annual fiscal savings in excess of \$395,000 in labor costs
- Course evaluations that yielded a high degree of learner satisfaction with content and method
- A 10% increase on the previous year in staff compliance with the requirements
- A commitment to the healthcare system's 'go green' practice environment by eliminating paper handouts, sign-in sheets, and binders
- A 24/7 accessible online classroom (Clark & Piercey, 2012).

Figure 2: Demonstrable Quality Upgrades from E-Learning Training Program

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